

Talisman: New Dynamics of Translation

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Abstract

Translation in languages, has been the most influential tool to connect people across the world since the dawn of civilizations. Translation is not only a means of communication but also the broad canvas to display the inmost cultural and emotional ethos. Meena Kandasamy like so many creative writers of the present world around took the charge with great deliberations. Talisman is a collection of articles and essays originally written in Tamil language by emerging political star Thirumaavlvann. He is considered to be the most powerful leader of Dalit liberation movement after Periyar. A number of political, social and cultural issues have been dealt with extreme clarity of the point of view. Meena Kandasamy translates with great enthusiasm.

Keywords: Dalit movement, marginals, subaltern, Sangam Literature

Introduction

Ilavenil Meena Kandasamy was born in Nineteen Hundred and Eighty Four in the city of Chennai, Tamil Nadu. Both of her parents were in scholastic profession. In her early age she developed interest in poetry. Under the impression of a female celluloid star in Bollywood, she adopted the name Meena. Pursuing her higher education, she set out for the state of Kerala. Her first independent social exposure occurred in Kerala. Later on, she did her Ph.D. from Amma University Chennai. She started poetic composition at the age of seventeen. She earned her doctorate in Social-linguistics in English. Her creative writings characteristically deal with caste-annihilation, feminism and linguistic identity of marginals and down-trodden. In this way her poetry is a tool for activism. Her first collection Touch that has the Foreword by Kamala Das. It was published in the year 2006. Ms. Militancy appeared next year. Her two poems Mascara and My Lover Speaks of Rape brought first prize in all india Poetry Competition. Her works published in several anthologies and journals including Anthology of Contemporary Indian Poetry, Kavya Bharati, Indian Literature, Poetry International Web, Muse India, Outlook, and The Indian Express. She was invited to participate in an International Writing Programme at the University of Iowa in two thousand and nine. She was selected the Charles Wallace India Trust Fellow. At the

University of Kent in the Year two thousand and eleven, she took part in *Asylum Jazz Poetry Concert*. That was organised in Pittsburgh. She was also an important feature in the *Fourteenth Poetry Africa International Festival, Durban* in 2010 and The Jaipur Literature Festival in 2011. She was also shortlisted as short-fiction women writer of the age less than forty years and who hailed from South Asia by Zubaan Books New Delhi. She published *Gypsy Goddess* in 2014.

Meena Kandasamy very closely observes in her works the issues regarding caste and gender and the social stigma based on that. She has to face threats also from right wing writers for her fearless criticism of social malpractices. She is also an active member of WNNI- *The Network of Women In Media in India*. She translated original works from Tamil Language into English. Talisman by Thirumavallan and Thirukkural are best examples to display her passion as a translator. She also acted in a Malayalam movie *Oroalppakkam*. She has been recently awarded with *Herman Kesten Prize* by PEN Centre, Germany in 2022. Her notable works are as follows-Talisman 2003, Touch 2006, Ms Militancy 2010, Waking is Another Dream 2010, The Gypsy Goddess 2014, This Poem will Provoke You 2015, When I Hit you: or, A portrait of the Writer as a Young Wife 2017, We are not the Citizens 2018, Exquisite Cadavers 2019, The Orders were to Rape You 2021,

Thirukkural: The Book of Desire 2023. Presently she is living in the East London City at U.K. During one hour long Zoom Meeting conversation with us on January 10, 2024 she was there at Belgium then. Objective of this study is to trace Humanistic Perspectives in the works of Meena Kandasamy. She is an active political figure. Her presence on media forums is now supposed to be a matter of pride. Her outspoken statements set her stand on the side of radical activists. She has too much admiration and so many awards to her credit abroad. Her recognition in the homeland is not so bright as it must be. This Thesis is a mere humble attempt to put her voice assertively. The extremism that shadows her works from time to time is only a remedial way of suppressed utterances. She is a Humanist at heart. That's why her works need to be analysed through humanistic perspectives. The Methodology adopted herein is descriptive and analytical in nature. Original texts of primary sources have been thoroughly ransacked and findings have been put forth with utter honesty. Many a fact has been explained in the light of a conversation that we successfully had with the author herself to get the feel of her pulse on different issues.

Meena Kandasamy is also an enthusiastic author of translated works. She is credited to have translated several pieces of writings, the works of different contents. But two of her collections of translated writings are supposed to be of much worth. No doubt, the number of works she translated is very scanty but they bear the testimony of life like original creations. The spirit in translated works is not tedious or repetitive. Her first translation is Talisman. As its title suggests this book was published in December 2004 by Bhatkal & Sen Kolkata. This book contains the English translation of the articles and the essays originally written in Tamil language by Thirumaavalvan. He is an emerging star of extreme emotions of the dalit liberation movement. He is supposed to be the most prominent dalit intellectual in Tamil Nadu after Periyar. He is the emerging heroic figure in the eyes of the world media. In the beginning of the new millennium it was the strength of his voice that inspired the marginalised to hit back. His essays are full of insights that assimilate a wide range of subjects. He describes all the facets of Tamil life. He is much interested in describing vividly the ways of Tamil people and their response to a given circumstances. The social, cultural, political, and economic outlook of the people of this region find a comfortable room in the essays of Thirumaavalvan. He boasts of his heritage. He is proud of his people and their traditions. But a sharp reverse to this, he does not keep a closed eye towards the plight of his community. He speaks harsh against the caste based discrimination and violence. These are highlighted issues in his discourses.

Materials and Methods

The methodology adopted for this study is qualitative in nature, focussing on content analysis and thematic exploration. The research involves textual analysis to interpret symbolic meaning, identify metaphysical elements, and discuss the narrative strategies used by Meena Kandasamy to convey the integration of Translation studies. By conducting a detailed analysis of this work, the researcher aims to uncover the underlying ideas. Through close examination of the text, the researcher will explore

how the author uses symbolism and metaphors to convey deeper technical innovations. By delving into the narrative strategies employed by Kandasamy, the study seeks to shed light on the intricate form of Translation studies offering new insights into the interconnectedness of several aspects of it. Ultimately, this qualitative study will contribute to a deeper understanding of how various dimensions interact and influence each other in the realm of Translation.

Thirumaavalvan's radical spirit impresses Meena Kandasamy to the very core of her heart. She is the sole admirer of his indomitable soul. Meena Kandasamy does not hesitate in taking the side of Thirumaavalvan when he is critical of the dominating social order and vertical discrimination of people based on caste in the society. He also strikes with full force upon Indian democracy. He jeers upon the fact that India is the largest democracy in the world. He flatly calls democracy in India 'mobocracy'. The distribution of power has been in the hands of already powerful men. System makes powerful more powerful and the weak are cursed to be trampled underfoot. State and its numberless agencies are just like thousand hooded snake eager to swallow the poor and marginalised. Political bases work with only aim to get or to secure the chair somehow. Bureaucracy is the greatest obstacle in the implementation of public welfare schemes. System has been hijacked by these middlemen. Police is but a tool in the hands of influential people. Judiciary runs like sponsored orchestra. Thirumaavalvan's writings are as militant and charismatic as his own personality. He is the new face of the movement of Tamil Nadu who has fought for equality at all levels. He has novel methods for tackling the problems. He infuses intense intellectual debates with a good deal of experimental politics. At places his faculty comes out of conventional scholarship. More than a leader, he is an important intellectual of the present time. He is champion of the issues of women's liberation. He also imbibes a liking for debatable issues as well. He speaks in the manner of calling a spade a spade on the controversial topics. He seems to be deeply concerned with the economic rights of the people. The establishment supports filling in the coffer of the rich silently and the poor stands calmly in the queue waiting endlessly for his turn. System that syphons money out of the reach of the poor needs to be uprooted. In a way all these cumulatively form a humanistic whole - a favourite term of Meena Kandasamy.

There are thirty four chapters in Talisman excluding Preface by Thirumaavalvan, Introduction by Gail Omvedt and Translator's Note by Meena Kandasamy. Thirumaavalvan produces hundreds of events declaring casteism rules the nation and not the law even today. He writes that dalits are forced to eat excrements, massacred by the police. Dalit panchayat president is terrorised into giving up of their position and prevented forcibly from exercising their rights to vote. Police slaughtered striking workers. Moreover, upper caste men agitated in the Southern districts of Tamil Nadu. Over the fact that a bus was named after a dalit freedom fighter. Thinkers around the world see this agitation as an upsurge and a thunder coming out of Tamil Nadu Cheri's. The other side is equally active with more brutal atrocities. But as much as suppression is imposed on marginalised so much more their assertion to fight back comes to the fore. Left wing ideology has its indelible stamp

on Thirumaavalvan. He is critical of all the Dravidian parties. He writes frankly that even some power-mongers from backward classes come to the power and forget everything on the root level so political leadership is a hopeless case. In one of the Chapters, he talks about Dr. Ambedkar and his contribution. Dr. Ambedkar had founded three political parties during his life time--

The independent Labour Party, The Socialist Scheduled Caste Federation of India and The Republican Party. He argues that Dr. Ambedkar attempted to destroy caste system and to relieve the oppression not only of the dalits but also of all Indians. His was a flexible Socio-political strategy. The fight for equality, against racism, casteism, patriarchy, and economic exploitation etc. occupy the vital part of his writings. The cases are not much different in The U S A and in India. He notices the struggling voice becoming stronger and stronger exerting direct impact on economy, politics and culture. His thought regarding Vaishnavism and Saivism is also radical. He confirms that both of these religious schools are rooted deep into Tamil soil. He forcefully confirms that orthodoxy, caste defending trends, among Vaishnavites, Savites, workers and Siddhas are non-Dravidian deplorable practices.

In the chapter His Excellency: Needed Again ! writer advocates for the reselection of K.R. Narayanan for the post of The President of The Republic of India. As a Dalit President he crushed the typical attitude of the people that President is just a powerless 'decorative doll'. He had also served as an Indian diplomate in several country but he always showed conscience for the grassroots people. As the President of the Republic of India, he repeatedly proclaimed the necessity of reservation of private sectors. K.R. Naraydan was of the view that it is failure of legal safeguard from sate subaltern that gives rise to extremism and terrorism. His opinion always bear the impact of humanitarianism, secularism, judiciousness and patience. Moreover, his approach to facts was matchless. Next chapter is No Need for the Election Commission! In this chapter giving certain examples writer suggests that the state machinery should not be crippled during election. A few malpractices in the process go unchecked because of powerlessness of the state machinery. So writer concludes that electoral procedure should have been made more democratic in its structure by taking in the states' expert help. The next chapter is the Party Colours on the Bulls' Horn: The President's Election. In this chapter writer seems to be unhappy over the fact of Abdul Kalam's selection as the President of India. Writer argues that Political forces in the centre be they ruling or opposition, are all anti-dalit. K.R. Narayan was disqualified because of his support of reservation in private sectors as well as Supreme Court of India. Abdul Kalam is supposed to be the Liberal and have a very soft corner for other religions. Title of the next chapter is 'They' Are Superior to Humans. In this chapter writer ponders over an incident that was staged in broad day light on May 21, 2002 in village Thinniyam in district Tiruchi. Three Dalits were branded with red-hot rods and forced to eat batman Faeces. Writer comments on it-

Even animals do not eat their excrement! But man has forced man to do it! More than those with the name

'human', that had the excrement-reasoning to force another to eat faeces; and mor than those that saw it with their eyes and heard it with their ears, and still remained dumb; the animals who do not eat their own excrement and do not force others to eat are superior! P. 122

The next Chapter is Eelam is the Foetus of the Tigers. In this chapter writer speaks against POTA. He says that it was meant to check terrorism and infiltration in Jammu and Kashmir. But very soon it was unleashed into Tamil Nadu. At once it became clear that the act was going to be used to break vengeance on political enmity. Rulers want all the citizens must do according to the party line ideology. It is the duty of citizen to respect the law but on the other hand it is also undemocratic that a citizen should behave according to all the wishes of those who enact and implement the law. The only objective is no alternative opinion or criticism should be there against the rulers. Such practices are sure to extend their hands to strangulate the throat of democracy. Title of the next chapter is Somalia in Tamil Nadu? Writer discusses the plight of hired farm labours, Tea plantation workers and weavers. He says in it, that those who work hard to clothe others are now, in tatters. Thirumavalan is critical of economic policies of Government of Tamil Nadu. Government is determined to exercise the policy of globalisation through privatisation and liberalisation. Writer is not very happy with the management of gruel-tanks. The emperor administration and a complacent approach lacking foresight- are the basis of closing down of factories one by one without employment of approaching workers suffering from hunger and starvation. Writer avers that Tamil Nadu is very soon to be a starvation state. This will be another Somaliya then. Title of the next chapter is A Raw Tamilian Is Needed! In this chapter writer reveals his heart with respect to Tamil language and culture. He looks into political affairs a number of shortcomings that are harmful for the soil and ethos of the region. He is very much disappointed over the deterioration of younger generation's feelings for the race and language. He finds it ridiculous that youths are building temples for actresses and offering oblation of milk on actor's cut outs.

Thirumaavalvan criticises harshly at the very outset the Tamil cinema. It is never bothered about the welfare of the people of Tamil Nadu. It has been trapped in the dominance of such organisations which like no attachment for the language. Movies which are short, Tamil language are given English Name. He describes the objection with an interesting story.

On one hand, this gang fleeces and the exploits the resources of Tamil Nadu; and on the other hand, they are castrating Tamilian youngsters to the extent of leaving them deprived of any feelings for language or race. That is why, a fan who wanted his wife to deliver when the film *Baba* was released, had urged the doctors to perform a caesarean section on his wife to bring forth the baby. That is, he wanted the entry of his child into this world to be a simultaneous occurrence with *Baba* hitting the theatres. To this level Tamilian youth are obsessed with cinema. p. 134

Title of the Next chapter is *Musharraf Is Also an Indian!* Writer in this chapter finds himself in the bewildered state over the fact of the quarrel among political parties. They have been blaming one another for the years. But as soon as election arrives their language softens. Who are the native Indians? is the question. He concludes that discrimination of any sort would sure to lead on utter confusion and indecisiveness. He is of the firm conviction that every person's thought should be more democratic and comprehensive. Title of the next chapter is *Even a Private Government Can Be Formed!* Writer is unhappy over the news of the privatisation of a few public sector undertakings. He argues that privatisation is said to be necessary in order to fulfil the need of globalisation. It has been imposed on people systematically. Starting of an industry in any corner of the world should go with no barriers. One must keep in mind that the aim of the public sector enterprises is to offer employment opportunities to public and to serve people. But in privatisation profit is the foremost motive. The World Trade Organisation (WTO) is leading the way ahead. The World Bank, the International Monetary Funds are already giving away so many liberty for the restricting private bodies. Education sector has also come under, the dominance of the private players. The technological institutions have been transferred into business enterprises. Analysing the facts Thirumavalan says that the prime motive behind the privatisation is a cruel intention that is to kill social justice. It is social justice policy of reservation that made it possible for subaltern to enter public sector enterprises. But because of privatisation such an opportunity would be snatched away.

Thematic Findings

Meena kandasamy concludes that privatisation is a way to globalization and globalization is to serve the interest of the imperialist super powers. In the Chapter *Why Was the Mark of Vishnu Thrust* she dissects the Pros and cons of the Introduction to the *Prohibition of Religious Conversion Ordinance* by Government of Tamil Nadu. She argues that from the time religions were formed, the right to conversion also existed. This law is severely devastating. Writer thinks that it is unconstitutional undemocratic to snatch away the right of religious conversion. In the next chapter *Tamil Rule Bloomed In the Vanni Forest!* writer shares her experience as a visitor to the Jaffna and Killinochi districts of northern Sri Lanka. She appreciates the education system, economic distribution, security and the way they take care of their martyr's memorials. She also draws a comparative picture of Sinhalese Eelam Administration. Most striking feature that impressed writer very much was development Tamil language as the military language. Not only cadres but also even the weapons of war were given names in Tamil. Thus, the forest of Vanni has the fragrance of Tamil Literature, Art, Culture, and Language in its purest form everywhere. In *ADMK Is Not a Periyar Movement* writer peeps into the earlier days of Periyar movement. She says that politician of modern day in order to having secured the chair they forget all about their promises. Religious leaders also have nothing important role to play in the upliftment of underdogs. Dalits have to fight their war on their own. In another chapter *Change of Name: Not Just a Retrieval of Language, but of History* writer talks the hegemony of English, Arabic, and

Sanskrit languages. People in Tamil Nadu consider it a matter of pride to take their name in northern Languages or in English. It is just against the spirit of Dravidian movement. She is also very angry over the fact that in many of the temples Chary people are not allowed to enter even today. She argues that names in other parts of the country indicate a religious identity but a Tamil name does not. She finalises his thought with the idea that the change of the name of a person, place, or a country is not just the retrieval of identity or language. It is the retrieval of a race's history. Next chapter is *Are Saivism and Vaishnavism Hindu Religion?* In this chapter writer confirms that Vaishnavism and Saivism are Tamil religions. So gods goddesses in the temples of Tamil Nadu should be prayed in Tamil Language. Along with advancement in trade and commerce Tamil people also excelled in spirituality. They developed indigenous pattern of worship.

Presence of Gods was the actual need of Tamil people. Spirituality of Tamilians is founded on history. The title of the next chapter is *Must Venmani be Fenced?* In this chapter writer commemorates the massacre of forty four people in the village Venmani on 25th December 1968. He sees not much change even in the protest march on the anniversary. It is mere a poor show of the brutal incident. Still they provide people with a new spirit for agitation. Title of the last Chapter is *Is the Tamil Land Infertile and Fallow ?* In this chapter writer considers the reason behind starvation and hunger Tamil Nadu. He says that the district of Tanjavur is the source of paddy for the entire Tamil Nadu. But because of insufficient rainfall there was this type of cruel drought and poverty. As government of Karnataka uses much of water from the River Cavery. Writer expresses his deep concerns over attacks on water bodies of Tamil Nadu by neighbouring province. Writer concludes the thought by the slogan 'Tamil Nadu is for the Tamilians alone' which he terms the only potent medicine.

Limitations

The primary limitations of this study lies in its focus on thematic study instead of technical aspect. Kandasamy offers a comprehensive understanding of how this theme operates across the entire body of works. Next presides politics as well as social in the thought process of the writer and Translator are written without any personal commentary on them. There is unavailability of secondary literature. This further added a sort of discomfort in the findings and conclusions. Thus the result is unipolar.

Conclusion

Meena Kandasamy's *Talisman* proves itself to be as a profound exploration into the dynamics of Translation studies. Each of the chapter deals with same prominent and burning social issues. A few of the topics have also been taken from the news papers. Kandasamy skillfully weaves together intricate stories that delve into the composites of human experience inciting reader's to contemplate the deeper meaning of the events described.

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